

How to Discover Gender in Energy World.

gEneSys Masterclass for Academic Teachers

The global energy transition is often presented as a technological revolution – powered by renewables, digitalisation, smart grids, and innovation. But beneath the infrastructure lies another transformation: a social and political struggle over who participates, who benefits, who leads, and whose knowledge counts.

The gEneSys International Masterclass invites academic teachers and practitioners and educators to explore the energy transition through a new lens – one that connects technology with power, equality, education, and social justice.

The energy sector remains one of the most gender-imbalanced sectors in Europe. Women are still underrepresented in engineering, energy governance, research, and leadership positions. At the same time, the transition to sustainable energy systems is creating entirely new professions, institutions, and forms of expertise.

The masterclass approaches the energy transition as:

- a technological process,
- a social transformation,
- a political and ethical challenge, and a question of justice and inclusion.

Participants will learn how to:

- recognise inequalities and exclusion mechanisms,
- connect STEM with social sciences and humanities,
- design more inclusive curricula and teaching materials,
- integrate gender and intersectional perspectives into energy education,
- motivate women and underrepresented groups to engage with energy careers,
- and rethink energy education as preparation for democratic participation in the transition.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - Culture, creativity and inclusive society - under grant agreement no. 101094326

Modules:

[Start module 0](#)

[Start module 1](#)

[Start module 2](#)

[Start module 3](#)

Module 0. How to Discover Gender in the Energy World

The introductory module of the gEneSys Masterclass invites participants to explore the energy transition through a gender and social justice lens. It challenges the common perception of energy as a purely technical field and highlights its social dimensions, including questions of power, participation, expertise, and representation.

Participants will examine how energy systems, policies, technologies, and infrastructures shape—and are shaped by—social inequalities. The module introduces the idea that the transition to sustainable energy is not only about decarbonisation, but also about creating more inclusive and equitable societies. It encourages critical reflection on who is recognised as an expert, who participates in decision-making, and whose needs and experiences are reflected in energy solutions.

By connecting gender perspectives with contemporary energy challenges, the module provides a foundation for integrating diversity, inclusion, and social equity into teaching, research, and professional practice.

Module 1. Energy Citizens

This module introduces participants to the growing role of energy communities in the transition towards sustainable and democratic energy systems. Energy communities are increasingly recognised as an important alternative to traditional, centralised energy models, enabling citizens to collectively produce, manage, and benefit from renewable energy.

Participants will explore the concept of energy citizenship, which goes beyond the role of passive energy consumers. The module highlights how individuals and local communities can become active contributors to energy systems, taking part in decision-making processes and sharing both the benefits and responsibilities of energy production and consumption.

Through practical examples and critical reflection, the module examines the social, economic, and environmental potential of energy communities. It also encourages participants to consider who participates in these initiatives, whose voices are heard, and how energy communities can become more inclusive and accessible.

Module 2. Professional Leaders

This module explores why the energy sector remains one of the most gender-imbalanced fields and why the ongoing energy transition presents a unique opportunity to challenge and transform these inequalities. Participants will examine the structural, cultural, and educational factors that contribute to gender disparities across the energy landscape.

The module addresses issues such as gender pay gaps, underrepresentation in leadership positions, stereotypes in education and career pathways, and barriers embedded in organisational and governance structures. It also considers how the rapid growth of green jobs may either reproduce existing inequalities or create new opportunities for greater inclusion and diversity.

Through critical analysis and practical examples, participants will identify key leverage points for change and reflect on the role of higher education in preparing a more diverse generation of energy professionals. By the end of the module, participants will better understand how gender equality can contribute to a more innovative, effective, and just energy transition.

Module 3. Teaching and Researching Energy in Higher Education

This module explores the critical role of higher education in shaping a just and inclusive energy transition. As energy systems become increasingly decarbonised, decentralised, and digitalised, universities play a key role in preparing future professionals, generating knowledge, and driving innovation.

Participants will examine how gender inequalities continue to influence energy education, particularly in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) fields, where women remain underrepresented among both students and academic staff. The module also highlights the often-overlooked contribution of Social Sciences and Humanities, which provide essential perspectives on gender, inclusion, and the social dimensions of energy transitions.

Through case studies, research findings, and practical reflections, participants will explore how curricula, teaching practices, and institutional cultures can either reinforce or challenge existing inequalities. The module encourages educators to rethink energy education in ways that integrate technical expertise with social responsibility, diversity, and gender awareness.

Authors:

Paulina Sekuta, PhD

Paulina Sekuta is an Assistant Professor at the Institute of Sociology and the Department of Medical Sociology at Jagiellonian University. Her research focuses on gender equality, institutional change in higher education and research, and the social determinants of health. She has extensive experience in developing and evaluating Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) within international and supporting institutional transformation across research organisations. Her work also addresses inclusive energy transitions, social determinants of healthy aging, and the reduction of structural inequalities through evidence-based solutions.

Aleksandra Wagner, PhD

Aleksandra Wagner is a researcher specialising in the social dimensions of the energy transition and the societal impacts of emerging technologies. Her work focuses on the relationships between technology, society, and public communication, including public acceptance of innovation, civic participation, and science communication. She has conducted research at Linköping University and the Leverhulme Centre for the Future of Intelligence at Cambridge University. Currently, she is developing post-humanist co-design methodologies and working on Plug&Chill, a social app that enables energy sharing between prosumers and electric vehicle drivers.

Marta Warat, PhD

Marta Warat is a sociologist and researcher specializing in gender equality policies, gender sociology, democracy, and citizenship. Her work examines the intersections of gender, power, and participation, with a particular focus on how democratic institutions and public policies shape opportunities for inclusion and civic engagement. She is interested in feminist approaches to citizenship, social justice, and democratic participation, exploring ways to strengthen equality and representation in both educational and public spheres.

Authors:

Tadeusz Rudek, PhD

Tadeusz Rudek is an Assistant Professor at the Institute of Sociology, Jagiellonian University, specialising in Science and Technology Studies and socio-technical change. His research explores how visions of the future shape technological development, public policy, and social responses to innovation. He has held research fellowships at Harvard University, King's College London, and ETH Zurich, and has worked on topics including energy transitions, artificial intelligence, climate change, and public health. His work focuses on making technological innovation more reflexive, democratic, and socially responsible.

Magdalena Klarenbach

Magdalena Klarenbach (Klara) is a researcher and educator, specialising in youth participation, climate engagement, and democratic innovation. Her work focuses on the intersections of climate change, social justice, and civic participation, with particular attention to empowering young people as agents of social change. She combines academic research with participatory and practice-based approaches, collaborating with civil society organisations and international projects to develop inclusive educational tools and democratic innovations that support engagement in sustainability transitions.

Arkadiusz Szlaga

Arkadiusz Szlaga (史建辉) is a PhD candidate and research assistant at the Institute of Sociology, Jagiellonian University. His research combines Science and Technology Studies, comparative sociology, and futures studies, focusing on how societies imagine and shape the future. He is currently developing the concept of an Ecology of Imaginaries and conducting comparative research on future-making practices in Poland and China. He has been stakeholder to several Horizon Europe projects, including PANTHEON and gEneSys, with a focus on stakeholder engagement, decarbonisation, and gender equality in the energy transition.